

Attacked, Harassed, Intimidated

A Narrative Review of Research and Action on Public Backlash Against Scientists in the Netherlands and Beyond

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Abstract

Public backlash against scientists, encompassing attacks, harassment, intimidation, hate, and threats from members of the public, has become a recurring feature of scientific work in the Netherlands and beyond. Despite growing attention and importance, the evidence base is scattered, terminology is used inconsistently, and responses are fragmented across institutions and countries. This report synthesizes the international academic literature in the form of a narrative review. It maps the conceptual vocabulary and summarizes empirical evidence on the prevalence of backlash (30–45% of academics; 50–80% of media-exposed scientists), its forms, drivers, gendered and racialized patterns, psychological and behavioral consequences, and individual and institutional responses, including a comparison with journalism and parliamentary politics. It reviews countermeasures in the Netherlands and internationally. Finally, it discusses limitations of the current support landscape, identifies lessons from adjacent professions, and proposes approaches for future research. A comprehensive appendix lists current initiatives and resources available to scientists, communicators, and institutions.

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Introduction

In December 2021, the Dutch virologist Marion Koopmans, Professor of Public Health Virology and Scientific Director of the Pandemic and Disaster Preparedness Center, posted an email she had received from an anonymous sender who called her a “filthy, dirty monster of Dachau” (NOS, 2021). Other messages reached her home as anonymous letters, and one social media post showed an image of a noose (de Volkskrant, 2022). Koopmans began commuting by car rather than by train, and during a family visit to an Amsterdam museum, security staff had to lock the doors as visitors recognized her and began shouting and banging (O’Grady, 2022).

Koopmans’ case is one of the most visible examples of attacks, harassment, and intimidation of scientists in the Netherlands. However, public backlash against science¹ is neither isolated nor confined to one discipline. The *Monitor externe intimidatie, haat en bedreiging van wetenschappers* documented protective measures for 59 academics at Dutch universities and institutes in 2023 alone, suggesting that the recorded cases are only the tip of the iceberg (UNL, 2024). Affected academics include political scientists studying far-right movements such as Sarah de Lange, migration historians such as Nadia Bouras, law philosophers such as Roland Pierik, scholars of gender studies, as well as agricultural and researchers working on climate change and the *stikstofcrisis* (Bouma, 2021; NOS, 2021). Universities themselves have also been targeted when issuing statements on contested political matters (UNL, 2024). Nonetheless, Dutch public trust in science remains high (Rathenau Instituut, 2025), but even a small minority of hostile actors can produce chilling and silencing effects on individual researchers, the scientific community, and the science communication ecosystem more broadly (Nölleke et al., 2023).

A growing complication is that public backlash increasingly intersects with pressure originating from within academia itself. University boards have, in several recent cases, been criticized for discouraging or restricting debate on contested geopolitical issues

(Breedveld, 2025; Cornelisse, 2025), and scholars on both ends of the political spectrum have reported that critical positions outside their colleagues’ mainstream attract pushback that they perceive as constraining their academic freedom. Dutch historian Steije Hofhuis, for example, has publicly described professional risks attached to taking critical positions in Dutch migration research, noting that the limited number of dissenting voices in his field “gives little room for debate” (Waling, 2025). Similar concerns have been raised about whether academic-freedom arguments can be invoked to insulate contested claims from scrutiny (Eski et al., 2026). These dynamics within academia, including criticism from fellow academics, board-level decisions about which debates to host, and informal collegial pressure, can turn into the public-facing backlash when controversies spill over into media coverage and online discourse (Buitenhof, 2026a, 2026b). The present report will nonetheless focus on *public* attacks, harassment, and intimidation directed at scientists from *outside* the academy, but intra-academic pressures are an important contextual backdrop to public backlash against scientists.

Evidence on the prevalence, forms, drivers, outcomes, and contextual factors of public backlash against science is, however, scattered and often anecdotal, and many analyses use a variety of terms without conceptual reasoning. Work on responses and countermeasures is similarly fragmented and often uncoordinated, and there is at present no synthesis that summarizes and organizes existing research and action on public attacks on scientists and scientific institutions. The present report provides such a synthesis in the form of a narrative review. It proceeds in five steps. Section 2 maps the conceptual vocabulary. Section 3 synthesizes the empirical evidence on the extent, consequences, and responses. Section 4 reviews countermeasures. Section 5 discusses the limitations of these countermeasures, derives lessons from adjacent fields, and suggests a research agenda. A comprehensive appendix systematizes initiatives and resources for scientists, communicators, and institutions in the Netherlands and beyond.

¹ This report uses the term “science” to refer to both the STEM sciences and the social sciences and humanities. Hence, the terms “scientist” and “scholar” are used interchangeably.

Conceptualizing Public Backlash Against Scientists

Established Concepts

One of the most developed concepts in scholarship on attacks, harassment, and intimidation targeting scientists is **hate speech**, which is broadly defined as expressions that attack, dehumanize, or disparage a person or group on the basis of an ascriptive characteristic such as ethnicity, religion, gender, or sexual orientation (Bilewicz & Soral, 2020; Hawdon et al., 2017; Schmid et al., 2024; Vergani et al., 2024). A more granular distinction from political communication and journalism research separates **intolerance**, i.e., dehumanizing slurs and discriminatory speech that aims to silence minorities and thus violates democratic norms, and **incivility**, i.e., vulgar tone, including name-calling, profanity, insults, and mockery (Papacharissi, 2004; Rossini, 2022; Stryker et al., 2016). Incivility primarily affects the register of debate by disrupting tone or venting frustration. Intolerance, by contrast, works towards marginalizing or excluding particular groups from public discourse. These concepts have been imported into science communication research by Anderson and Huntington (2017), Egelhofer et al. (2024), and Mede and Volk (2026), among others. They adapted these concepts to science communication, which, in contrast to political communication and journalism research, centers on truth claims and epistemological norms rather than on political authority or media practices.

Cursorily Used Terms

A second cluster of terms is widely deployed but only loosely defined. **Harassment** has been used as an umbrella for behaviors ranging from credibility attacks to insults, aggression, abuse, and coercion (Egelhofer et al., 2024; see also Menke & Seeger, 2026; Miller, 2023). **Threats** and **intimidation** appear in many empirical studies as discrete categories but rarely with formal definitions (Nogrady, 2021; O'Grady, 2022; Verhaeghe, 2023). **Hostility** is sometimes used as a blanket term covering aggressive, intimidating, or offensive language directed at scientists or their

work, encompassing both the stylistic register of attacks (the use of swear words or insults) and their intended function of expressing anger and silencing other discussants (König et al., 2019; Schmid & Werner, 2023; Väliverronen & Saikkonen, 2021b). One of the broadest umbrellas in current use is **backlash**. Following Mede and Volk (2026), it can be defined as acts aimed at challenging, disparaging, or harming individual scientists, science institutions, and science as an epistemic system.

Adjacent Phenomena

Several adjacent phenomena and related constructs have been discussed against the backdrop of the various forms of public backlash against scientists. **Contestation** is one of these phenomena, but typically connotes substantive disagreement with scientific claims rather than personal attacks on scientists (Metag & Wintterlin, 2026). **Science skepticism**, **science denial**, **conspiracy beliefs**, and **science-related populism** denote worldviews toward science that may, but need not, translate into hostile communication. The latter, theorized by Mede and Schäfer (2020), captures the belief that "ordinary people" rather than academic elites should determine what counts as legitimate knowledge and how it is produced. It can manifest in attacks on scholars and experts, accusing them of being ideologically biased and ignoring the practical needs of the general public (Sekerdej, 2025). **Political interference with science**, another phenomenon falling into the broad category of pushback against academia, refers to the use of state power (funding decisions, screening laws, public attacks by officials, vexatious freedom-of-information requests) to constrain research agendas and intimidate scholars (Halpern, 2015; KNAW, 2025). **Attacks on academic freedom**, as captured for instance in the Academic Freedom Index (Spannagel & Kinzelbach, 2022), are conceived as limitations to the broader institutional and individual right of researchers to choose research questions, methods, and topics, to teach, and to disseminate their work within and outside academia without external constraint. Scientists' safety from public attacks, harassment, and intimidation is therefore best understood as a necessary precondition for one specific component of academic freedom, i.e., the

freedom of academic exchange and dissemination, because scholars who self-censor under threat cannot fully exercise that component, even if their formal right to do so remains intact. Public-facing backlash thus differs from threats to the social safety of scientists on campus, such as sexual harassment, discrimination, or abuse of power.

Conceptual Nuances and Normative Considerations

An important analytical distinction that draws on Rossini's work on intolerance and incivility (2022) concerns the **substance** of public backlash (its arguments and content) and its **tone** (its register and emotional charge). Kumpel and Unkel (2023) show that audiences perceive these differently.

Accordingly, legitimate arguments delivered in an uncivil tone may be experienced as harassment, while illegitimate arguments delivered in a civil tone may pass without remark. Mede and Volk (2026) find a similar dynamic in qualitative interviews with university communicators, who tend to weigh tone more heavily than substance when assessing legitimacy. They argue that conflating incivility with substantive criticism risks pathologizing valuable forms of public engagement, such as scrutiny of technical errors, vested interests, scientific misconduct, and questionable research practices (see Mede et al., 2025).

Yet, the distinction between **valuable public feedback** and **illegitimate backlash** is blurry, since legitimate skepticism can shade into incivility and civil tone can mask intolerant content (Mede & Volk, 2026). Social movement research has conceptualized this distinction in terms of **normative** protest – i.e., peaceful, legal, morally acceptable means of criticism – and **non-normative** protest, i.e., illegal, violent, illegitimate actions (Teixeira et al., 2023; Zlobina & Gonzalez Vazquez, 2018). Public sphere scholarship suggests a similar differentiation into **deliberative** conceptions of the public sphere, which emphasize factual argumentation, civil tone, and equal participation, and **agonistic** conceptions, which hold that incivility and aggression may also be acceptable, particularly for marginalized voices (Dahlberg, 2001; Mouffe, 2002). Combined with the tone–substance

distinction, this yields a **continuum** from civil legitimate criticism (such as pointing out methodological flaws), through uncivil but lawful expression, to clearly illegitimate non-normative behaviors (defamation, threats of violence, doxxing, vandalism, physical attack).

Empirical Evidence

The empirical literature on the various forms of public backlash against scientists has grown rapidly since 2018, driven first by studies of women scholars on social media (Veletsianos et al., 2018) and then by several investigations during the COVID-19 pandemic spanning multiple national contexts (e.g., Nogrady, 2021; O'Grady, 2022). However, many of these investigations relied on online surveys with self-selected samples, modest response rates, and varying scope and definitions of backlash. Within these limits, findings nonetheless converge on consistent patterns. Paralleling this line of research are surveys consistently identifying substantial harassment originating within academia itself (Aguilar & Baek, 2020; Peetz et al., 2024; Verhaeghe, 2023). These are not the focus of the present review but important to contextualize what follows.

Extent, Forms, Drivers, Contextual Factors, and Comparison with Neighboring Fields

Survey-based estimates of the **overall prevalence** of attacks, harassment, and intimidation cluster in a concerning high range. National-level surveys consistently report that **30–45%** of academics have experienced at least one form of harassment over reference periods of months to years: The German KAPAZ study (Blümel, 2024) and Verhaeghe's (2023) survey of Flemish researchers both report 45%, Oksanen et al.'s (2022) Finnish data 30%, Seeger et al.'s (2024) survey of German, Austrian, and Swiss communication scholars 46%, and Peetz et al.'s (2024) multi-country survey across climate, food, plant science, and astronomy 41%. Among **media-active scientists**, prevalence rises clearly: A Finnish survey of media-active researchers finds that around 60% had received disturbing feedback during public

appearances, with politicized topics (immigration, gender, climate) most affected (Väliverronen & Saikkonen, 2021a). A *Nature* survey of scientists who had given media interviews about the COVID-19 pandemic finds that more than two-thirds reported negative experiences after speaking in news media or posting comments on social media (Nogrady, 2021). A *Science* survey of 510 COVID-19 researchers shows that 38% have experienced at least one type of attack, “ranging from insults to death threats, delivered on social media, by email or phone, or sometimes even in person”, with 53% never having experienced attacks before the pandemic (O’Grady, 2022). A Global Witness (2023) survey of climate researchers reports a percentage of 39% (rising to 73% among the most media-active researchers), and the Spanish Science Media Centre (2024) reports that 51% had suffered an attack after communicating about their work, with the social media platform X being the principal venue. Chen et al. (2025), surveying 732 academic authors writing for *The Conversation Canada*, finds that 27.5% had received toxic comments that were motivated predominantly by ideological disagreement (70.1%). Marcinkowski et al.’s (2025) survey of 4,207 German scientists, the largest single-country study to date, finds that 15% of those who appeared in news media and nearly 30% of those active in online media or in-person events had experienced hostility after speaking publicly about COVID-19. Jupskås et al. (2025), in a survey of 103 Norwegian political scientists, report a lower 14% prevalence over five years, attributing this to Norway’s comparatively low societal polarization. Together, these surveys converge on a backlash base rate of **30–40% among general academics** and **50–80% among media-exposed academics**.

Forms of backlash that are most common tend to cluster at the lower end of severity (e.g., trolling, condescending comments, attacks on competence) and sometimes even within the scope of potentially valuable criticism (e.g., credibility complaints to superiors or funders), each affecting ca. 20–35% of academics in the Flemish and German surveys (Blümel, 2024; Verhaeghe, 2023). Severe, illegitimate, and illegal forms of backlash are far rarer: In Flanders, 6% were blackmailed or received legal threats, 3% received threats of physical violence, and under 1% experienced actual violence. Severity rates are noticeably higher among media-exposed COVID-19

researchers, where 22% of Nogrady’s (2021) sample received threats of physical or sexual violence and 15% reported death threats. Peetz et al. (2024) provide a broad taxonomy of backlash, identifying “unwelcome behavior” (46%), budget cuts (34%), formal complaints (34%), pressure to redirect research (31%), adverse information spread about scientists (26%), and online abuse (15%). Doerfler et al. (2021) document the networked character of much harassment, in which large numbers of attackers, mobilized through social media coordination, generate a volume and velocity qualitatively different from other forms of backlash outside the Internet. Waisbord (2020) describes a similar dynamic among US journalists as “mob censorship”.

Channels of backlash vary in intensity. Email and on-campus encounters are consistently identified as high-intensity channels (Verhaeghe, 2023). X and Facebook predominate in backlash on social media, whereas Instagram and LinkedIn are less populated with hate, harassment, and hostility (Global Witness, 2023; Mede & Volk, 2026; Nogrady, 2021; Science Media Centre Spain, 2024). Peters (2024) analyzed 6,000 tweets directed at six visible German virologists during the COVID-19 pandemic and found that 17.3% contained incivility and 17.5% explicit concerns about epistemic trustworthiness, suggesting that doubts about scientific credibility are frequently expressed with uncivil tone.

Argumentative themes of public backlash have been systematically analyzed by Medina et al. (2021), for example. They coded 762 hostile online comments responding to US researchers’ work on hate groups and identified seven main themes: Attacks on research quality, conspiracy claims, justifications of racism, accusations of corruption, partisan political comments, anti-academic sentiment, and extreme action-threatening comments. Their results show that a recurring rhetorical strategy is invoking “common sense” to delegitimize scientific findings. Peters (2024) and Galpin and Vernon (2024) document partly overlapping repertoires in German virologist and UK Brexit-era contexts.

Sociodemographic and disciplinary differences are pronounced. Female scientists report higher overall exposure and substantially higher exposure to gendered and sexualized forms of backlash (Global

Witness, 2023; Peetz et al., 2024; Verhaeghe, 2023). 11.7% of Flemish female researchers had received unwanted sexual messages versus 7.4% of men. 13% of women in the Global Witness (2023) climate scientists sample had been threatened with sexual violence. In a notable exception to this pattern, Chen et al. (2025) find that for academic authors at *The Conversation Canada*, race and disability were significant predictors of toxic comments while gender was not, suggesting that the visibility of demographic differences may depend on the publishing venue and on which features of the author's identity are most visible to commenters. Ethnic minorities and academics with chronic illness also report substantially higher exposure to backlash (e.g., 62% and 43% in Flanders; Verhaeghe, 2023). Another factor is career level, with professors typically reporting more attacks than non-tenured scholars (Seeger et al., 2024). Also, discipline matters, with climate science being most exposed in the global Peetz et al. (2024) sample, humanities and social sciences in the German and Flemish data, and life sciences in the German pandemic data (Marcinkowski et al., 2025). Jupskås et al. (2025) find that within political science, scholars of controversial topics (extremism, gender, environmental politics, racism) reported harassment at more than twice the rate of others (21% versus 9%). Pearson et al. (2024) report that among online extremism scholars across Europe and North America, female researchers, researchers of color, and junior researchers are affected in particular ways, with nearly a quarter of all interviewees having received death threats and almost half having had no prior awareness of the risks of their research. Rodriguez et al. (2025), in a content analysis of 994 Facebook comments responding to LGBTQIA+ research recruitment advertisements, similarly find that researchers are frequently dehumanized and LGBTQIA+ identities pathologized through stigma communication. Qualitative work interprets these patterns as discursive boundary-policing: Galpin and Vernon (2024) argue that abuse directed at women, racialized, and LGBTQ+ scholars functions as discursive violence, i.e., a mechanism through which gendered, sexualized, or racialized bodies are positioned as incompatible with the figure of "the expert".

Perpetrators have barely been studied so far. Exceptions are Gligorić et al. (2025) and Chinn et al.

(2023), for example. Across two preregistered studies, Gligorić et al. (2025) find that science cynicism (the perception that scientists are incompetent and corrupt) was the most consistent predictor of approval of harassment, alongside threat perceptions and the dark personality traits of psychopathy and narcissism. Chinn et al. (2023), in two-wave US panel data, distinguish distrust of science from the perception of scientists as a social threat, finding that the latter is far more strongly associated with support for excluding scientists from policy-making and for retributive actions against them. This suggests that organized backlash is driven less by epistemic disagreement than by perceived value conflicts.

Comparisons with adjacent backlash-facing professions, specifically journalists and politicians, put the above-mentioned findings into perspective. For **journalists**, the Dutch PersVeilig (2021) survey of 689 reporters found that 82% had experienced some form of aggression or threat, 66% verbal aggression in the past 12 months, 51% threats or intimidation, 17% physical aggression, and 20% legal threats including Strategic Lawsuit Against Public Participation (SLAPP), with 13% having considered leaving the profession entirely. UK survey data from the Reuters Institute show that hate speech, public discrediting, and intimidation are the three most common safety threats to journalists (Panievsky & Blumell, 2025), and a 15-country UNESCO survey found that 73% of women journalists had experienced online violence, with 20% subsequently experiencing offline harm (UNESCO, 2021). In the US, a 2024 survey of 610 local journalists, conducted by the International Women's Media Foundation (IWMF), documents that 36% had been threatened with or experienced physical violence, 33% digital violence, 28% legal threats, and 24% sexual harassment in the course of their work (International Women's Media Foundation, 2024). Science journalists specifically seem to be exposed at rates similar to other journalists rather than to scientists, although dedicated surveys remain rare. A 2025 ABSW-UWE online survey of a small sample of UK-based science journalists found that 50% had experienced workplace discrimination or harassment, 34% had experienced online abuse or harassment in connection with their science-journalism work (most commonly around COVID-19, vaccines, and climate change), and 33% reported

avoiding certain subjects for fear of online abuse, with only 25% having received any training or support to cope with it (Ridgway, 2025). For **politicians**, the Dutch *Monitor integriteit en veiligheid 2024* reports that 45% of decentralized political officeholders (mayors, council members, water-board administrators) experienced aggression in the past year, with online incidents dominating (Ministry of the Interior and Kingdom Relations, 2024). The 2026 Inter-Parliamentary Union report on political violence against parliamentarians, drawing on national surveys in Argentina, Benin, Italy, Malaysia, and the Netherlands plus a global survey, finds that 71% of MP respondents had experienced violence by the public (online, offline, or both), with online abuse running between 65% and 77% across the case studies (Inter-Parliamentary Union, 2026). For Dutch MPs specifically, 17% reported offline violence and around 80% perceived a worsening trend over the past five years. Cross-EU comparative data show that 81% of attacked German local politicians reported physical or mental effects, and Irish parliamentarians reported that 94% had experienced some form of threat, harassment, abuse, or violence (Zamfir, 2025). Taken together, these figures suggest that **base rates of public-facing hostility are higher among politicians and journalists than among scientists**, but that media-active scientists in highly politicized fields approach the politician and journalist rates. The forms, drivers, and gendered patterns of attacks are noticeably similar across all three groups, suggesting a partially shared backlash logic targeting public-facing communicators.

Consequences

Psychological effects are widely documented: More than 40% of Nogrady's (2021) media-active COVID-19 researchers said they experienced emotional or psychological distress. In the Global Witness (2023) sample of climate researchers, 51% of those who were harassed reported anxiety, 21% depression, and 32% of women reported sleep problems. Verhaeghe (2023) finds that frequently intimidated academics lost on average 2.11 points on an 11-point happiness scale, and Peetz et al. (2024) report that 70% of intimidated scientists felt stress (40% often or a lot). Qualitative studies consistently describe stress,

sleeplessness, and hyper-vigilance about online presence as consequences of attacks, harassment, and intimidation (Doerfler et al., 2021; Gosse et al., 2021; Nölleke et al., 2023; Veletsianos et al., 2018).

Professional and behavioral consequences center on self-censorship and disengagement. Verhaeghe (2023) finds that 38% of Flemish academics felt hesitant to voice opinions on particular topics, 28% to communicate about their research, and 28% to stay in academia. Peetz et al. (2024) report that more than 40% of attacked scientists felt their career prospects had worsened, 35% had cut back on collaboration, and 18% had quit their job. The Global Witness (2023) report finds that 41% of climate scientists had become less likely to post on social media, and 17% of those who experienced negative episodes in Spain stopped media engagement entirely (Science Media Centre Spain, 2024). These results indicate a "**chilling effect**" (Nölleke et al., 2023; see also Seeger et al., 2024). However, this effect may be overstated. For example, Marcinkowski et al. (2025) distinguish a **flight or fight** dynamic: Scientists who perceive harassment as serious and consider withdrawal engage in "danger control" and reduce their engagement. However, those who feel threatened but do not consider retreat realistic engage in "fear control" and maintain or even increase their engagement despite backlash. Nölleke et al. (2023) corroborate these findings: Their interviews with 24 Austrian scientists show that many did not withdraw from public engagement as "their motivations to meet the needs of an unsettled public outweighed the experience of being harassed online" (p. 546).

Systemic consequences result from individual-level effects: If harassment disproportionately affects women, ethnic minorities, junior scholars, and politically sensitive researchers, and if these groups are also more likely to step back from public communication, then the public-facing scientific community becomes systematically narrower than the underlying research community (Gosse et al., 2021; Veletsianos et al., 2018). More broadly, normalization of backlash against science can produce a spiral-of-silence dynamic in which the absence of credible voices creates space for less credible ones (Doerfler et al., 2021; Mede & Volk, 2026).

Individual and Institutional Responses

Individual responses to attacks, harassment, and intimidation follow a pattern described in terms of **proactive** and **reactive** coping (Veletsianos et al., 2018) or in terms of support across **micro, meso, and macro levels** (Houlden et al., 2022). Houlden et al.'s (2022) online survey of 182 affected scholars shows that microsystem supports (friends and family) are rated as helpful by large majorities, whereas mesosystem supports are often perceived as ineffective: 47% report that outreach to their institution offers no help, and 41% say that reporting incidents to social media platforms is not helpful at all.

The most common immediate response strategy is ignoring or deleting hostile messages, often combined with blocking the perpetrator (Celuch et al., 2022; Nogrady, 2021; Nölleke et al., 2023; Seeger et al., 2024). Reporting to platforms, employers, and the police occurs much less often. 44% of harassed researchers in the *Nature* sample had not informed their employer at all (Nogrady, 2021). And in the *Science* survey fewer than 10% of harassed COVID-19 researchers had received employer support of any specific kind (O'Grady, 2022). Proactive strategies (pseudonymization, reduced personal disclosure, avoidance of certain topics) are reported across the qualitative literature (e.g., Mede & Volk, 2026), particularly by women scholars (Gosse et al., 2021; Veletsianos et al., 2018). Mede and Volk (2026), interviewing university communicators in nine countries, find that institutions are often motivated to engage with substantive criticism delivered in a civil tone and also respond to clearly illegitimate attacks by high-status sources. However, criticism by low-status actors falls into a gap, treated as too small to escalate but too costly to engage.

A noteworthy finding from Peetz et al. (2024) concerns the **paradox of support**. External sources (friends, family, colleagues) were rated as supportive by 80–91% of intimidated scientists who consulted them, compared with only 27% for internal HR and 39% for senior management. Support from senior management mattered strongly for job retention: With supportive management, the rate of scholars quitting their job stayed at 4–5% regardless of stress level, while with unsupportive management, quit rates rose to 18–22%.

Institutional responses are increasingly visible but unevenly evaluated. In Verhaeghe's (2023) Flemish data, 80–90% of academics regarded as helpful the training of supervisors, the provision of institutional legal and psychological support, support to involve the police, and the promotion of reporting points.

A complementary line of work on response strategies focuses on interventions of **bystanders**, i.e., other people observing attacks, harassment, and intimidation, for example on social media. Egelhofer et al. (2026) report a transdisciplinary co-creation process in Germany that produced an Instagram campaign modeling bystander interventions. Their experiments found that short videos increased bystanders' willingness to engage in supportive actions, and the campaign reached over 10 million views. Obermaier et al. (2025) further show that perceived political and critical digital media literacy are key predictors of such bystander intervention, suggesting that public-education investments may be a complementary route to behavioral interventions.

Countermeasures and Support Structures

The Dutch Landscape

The Netherlands has, in comparative European perspective, a relatively well-developed institutional infrastructure for responding to public attacks, harassment, hate, intimidation, threats, and other forms of backlash against scientists, science communication professionals, and scientific institutions. One of its centerpieces is **WetenschapVeilig** (SafeScience), a nation-wide platform offering structured guidance (UNL, 2021) and a 24/7 online and telephone hotline for scientists, managers, and employers that have been facing and want to prepare better for public backlash (WetenschapVeilig, 2022). It was launched in November 2022 by the Dutch Universities (UNL), the Dutch Research Council (NWO), and the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW) and is supported by the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science (KNAW, 2022a). Reports about backlash are forwarded to the relevant employer, who contacts

the scholar to organize tailored support such as security measures, removal of online contact details, legal advice, mental-health support, and police liaison. Many Dutch universities have integrated WetenschapVeilig with their internal support measures (e.g., Maastricht University, 2022; Radboud Universiteit, 2022; Utrecht University, 2022).

Moreover, **individual universities** have begun to develop their own complementary procedures, strategies, and infrastructures. A few focus specifically on public harassment, intimidation, and threats (e.g., the University of Amsterdam, n.d.), but university-level support measures are embedded within broader social safety policies. Beyond such formalized arrangements, however, day-to-day responses at most institutions tend to rely on ad hoc and improvised case-by-case support from communications officers, confidential advisors, and public relations managers (Mede & Volk, 2026).

Some Dutch institutions have engaged in complementary efforts, including the KNAW's **Committee for the Freedom of Scientific Pursuit**, which has produced position papers and reports on intimidation, knowledge security, and academic freedom (KNAW, 2022b, 2023, 2025). At the supra-national level, **Dutch leadership** has been visible in the UNESCO Programme on the Freedom and Safety of Scientists, launched in 2023-2024 with the Netherlands as a key driver and the UNESCO (2024) report as its first publication.

Initiatives Across Europe

National initiatives outside the Netherlands have proliferated since 2023, particularly in the German-speaking world. **Scicomm-Support**, launched by Wissenschaft im Dialog and Bundesverband Hochschulkommunikation, operates a helpline for scientists and science communicators in Germany, Austria, and Switzerland (Scicomm-Support, 2023). The **KAPAZ** project has produced a representative survey of researchers, a legal opinion on institutional duties, and train-the-trainer programs (HIIG, 2025), and the **GERDEA** project addresses right-wing hostility specifically (GERDEA-Forschungsverbund und Bundesverband Mobile Beratung e.V., 2025). Further established national initiatives in other

European countries are currently missing. Beyond national programs, several European universities have implemented their own response strategies. Some are embedded in institutional processes: The University of Vienna, for example, has a dedicated threat management team that handles public attacks and intimidation of staff and students (University of Vienna, n.d.). However, most strategies are less institutionalized, with help pages or social-media guidance documents serving as the primary internal reference (e.g., University of Cambridge, n.d.).

European initiatives include, for example, the Horizon Europe **PREPARED** project, which published the *Freedom from Harassment for Scientists Is Essential* report in 2025 (Schroeder et al., 2025). Further initiatives support *researchers at risk* in the classic sense, i.e., scholars persecuted in their countries of origin. **Inspireurope** (2022–2025), coordinated by Scholars at Risk Europe and funded by the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, builds national fellowship schemes (such as Germany's Philipp Schwartz Initiative and France's PAUSE programme) and informs EU policy (SAR Europe, 2025). The **MSCA4Ukraine** (2022) and **SAFE** (2024) fellowship programmes apply this model to specific situations.

Global, Researcher-Led, and Sectoral Resources

Several non-European resources are often used in European practice. The US-based **Researcher Support Consortium** (2024) toolkit is one of the most detailed resources available, covering policy templates, reporting forms, response procedures, and FOIA (Freedom of Information Act) management. The **AoIR Risky Research Guide** (2025) provides risk-assessment frameworks adapted to scholars working on disinformation, extremism, LGBTQ+ rights, and platform governance (AoIR, 2025), and the US **National Academy of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine** maintains a resource hub for researchers under threat (NASEM, 2025). For specific high-risk fields, the **Society for Neuroscience** has published best practices for animal-research scientists (SfN, 2024). **Civic Laboratory's** *When Your Research Is Attacked* guide synthesizes self-protection strategies (CLEAR, 2025). And the **Science Media Centres** in the

UK, Spain, and Australia/New Zealand have published advice on engaging the media constructively when targeted, including the AusSMC's *Handling Online Harassment* online toolkit (Australian Science Media Centre, 2024; Science Media Centre Spain, 2024; Science Media Centre UK, 2019).

The Centre for the Study of Democratic Institutions at the **University of British Columbia** has published a 2025 policy brief proposing a wraparound institutional support framework integrating physical safety, cybersecurity, mental health, communications, legal, equity-and-inclusion, and HR support (Mathews et al., 2025), operationalizing the ecological framework of Houlden et al. (2022). A complementary Canadian effort, Wright et al.'s (2022) policy briefing for the **Royal Society of Canada**, sets out seven recommendations addressing the federal funding agencies, the federal government, and the postsecondary sector, including a more nuanced approach to knowledge mobilization requirements that takes safety into account.

Practitioner-oriented guidance for individual researchers includes Nogrady's (2022) *Nature* toolkit on protecting oneself from online abuse and the Center for Countering Digital Hate's (2019) *Don't Feed the Trolls* handbook, which sets out a harm-minimization framework for public figures dealing with coordinated trolling. The **Union of Concerned Scientists** maintains an *Anti-Science Actions* tracker (UCS, 2026), and other widely-cited operational resources include the **PEN America Online Harassment Field Manual**, the **Climate Science Legal Defense Fund**, and **Faculty First Responders**, with the UNESCO programme providing the overarching international framework (PEN America, 2024; UNESCO, 2024). A comprehensive catalog can be found in the appendix.

Discussion and Conclusion

Limitations of Current Support Measures

Despite the rich ecosystem of countermeasures against public backlash, current initiatives and resources have several limitations. First, there is often **little coordination** across institutions and across

countries. Resources are dispersed, toolkits and helplines are duplicated, and cross-border learning is limited. Second, **system-level measures are underdeveloped** relative to individual- and institutional-level support; legislation, platform regulation, and prosecution practice tends to be deficient in many countries. WetenschapVeilig provides good coordination, but scholars and KNAW have called for stronger criminal-justice responses, social-media regulation, and constitutional protection of academic freedom (KNAW, 2025; Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, 2024). Third, very **few existing measures have been empirically validated**. The Egelhofer et al. (2026) bystander intervention is a notable exception, and in the broader hate-speech literature, Hangartner et al.'s (2021) field experiment provides causal evidence that empathy-based counterspeech can reduce racist hate speech on Twitter. Their study complements Garland et al.'s (2022) longitudinal evidence that organized counterspeech is associated with shifts in online discourse. However, a 2022 systematic review concludes that the evidence base for what works to reduce online hate remains thin (Windisch et al., 2022). Fourth, several existing resources suffer from **limited visibility and uptake**. The 2024 Dutch Monitor explicitly notes that many threatened scientists do not use WetenschapVeilig (UNL, 2024). Fifth, the dominant logic of current measures is vulnerability-reducing and perpetrator-discouraging, with comparatively **little being done to strengthen resilience among scientists or solidarity among publics** (Egelhofer et al., 2026; Mede & Volk, 2026; Nölleke et al., 2023). Sixth, current responses underserve the blind spot identified by Mede and Volk (2026), i.e., **backlash from low-status sources is treated as too costly to engage** and too minor to escalate.

Lessons from Adjacent Fields: Journalism and Politics

Public-facing scientists are not the only public communicators confronting an increasingly hostile environment. Journalists and politicians face structurally similar challenges (see section 3.1). The institutional responses developed in those fields offer

several lessons that can inform more effective institutional responses to backlash against scientists.

From journalism, three lessons stand out. First, the Dutch **PersVeilig** demonstrates the value of multi-stakeholder initiatives. Launched by the Dutch Association of Journalists (NVJ), the Association of Editors-in-Chief, the Netherlands Prosecution Service, and the Police, it coordinates with prosecution authorities and uses a 200% sentencing enhancement guideline for crimes against journalists (PersVeilig, 2021). This joint-forces approach allows for coordinated, more powerful resilience against public hate, harassment, and threats. WetenschapVeilig is structurally similar to PersVeilig, but criminal-justice coordination is less formalized. The PersVeilig model suggests this gap could be closed. Second, the **IWMF's identity-informed risk assessment** framework recognizes that risk varies by gender, race, and sexual orientation, and trains journalists and editors to plan accordingly (International Women's Media Foundation, 2024). Equivalent identity-informed, target-specific risk assessment is not yet a standard component of most responses to backlash against scientists at universities. Third, the journalism literature tends towards a consensus that **editor and newsroom-manager engagement** is a decisive determinant of journalists' sense of safety. Department chairs, deans, and rectors at universities should therefore be aware of their central role in shaping the safety climate for academic public engagement.

From parliamentary politics, the recent Inter-Parliamentary Union (2026) global study of 519 parliamentarians across five countries (including the Netherlands) suggests four clusters of institutional recommendations that may compensate for some gaps in responses to public backlash against scientists: First, **prevention, security, and data collection**, including security and safety protocols and regular cross-national prevalence monitoring. Second, **reporting and protection** through a permanent, independent, neutral, centralized support mechanism, with specialized digital-safety units modeled on the UK's Fixed Threat Assessment Centres. Third, **visibility and awareness**, including advertising available support measures within institutions and sensitization among the general population through public campaigns. Fourth,

accountability, including review of whether existing legislation provides adequate deterrence and whether higher penalties for crimes against targets of attacks are warranted (Inter-Parliamentary Union, 2026; Zamfir, 2025). Several EU countries have introduced legislation classifying offences against politicians as aggravated offences (France's 2024 law, Sweden's 2020 Criminal Code amendment, Germany's 2021 expansion of §188 StGB). This regulatory move has no clear equivalent for scientists so far. The Dutch **Threatened Politicians Team** at the Hague police, which systematically analyzes all reported threats and initiates investigations when criminal thresholds are met, offers a model that could be replicated for scientists, complementing rather than duplicating WetenschapVeilig.

The general pattern is that scientific institutions are slightly behind journalism and parliamentary politics in formalizing system-level responses but are catching up. Importantly, none of the three fields has solved the problem of empirical evaluation of countermeasure effectiveness, which remains a shared challenge.

An Agenda for Future Research and Action

Although a systematic, evidence-informed assessment and evaluation of the Dutch situation is missing, this review suggests that the Netherlands has **comparatively well-developed countermeasures** against attacks, harassment, and intimidation targeting scientists. These countermeasures include the national reporting platform WetenschapVeilig, institutional contact points and manuals across many universities, the KNAW committee structure, a published practical guide (UNL, 2021), and a national monitor (UNL, 2024), alongside comparatively strong recognition of the problem among university leaders. But at the same time, the Netherlands may also face **higher demand** for such countermeasures because of the country's relatively pronounced public-service orientation in science communication, which makes outreach and engagement core components of scientific labor. That public-facing orientation, while valuable, also invites public backlash and resentment beyond positive, affirmative, or constructive feedback and dialogue. There is therefore room for improvement on the **preventive** side, for example by

systematically integrating media training and public-engagement safety awareness into PhD education and by ensuring sufficient budget allocation to response measures at national and institutional levels. Equally, the **reactive** side could be strengthened, for example by developing standardized backlash-response protocols that can be shared and applied across institutions, reducing the current reliance on improvised case-by-case responses by communications officers, confidential advisors, and PR managers. Beyond the preventive–reactive distinction, on a **structural** level, there is an apparent disconnect between individual, institutional, and national responses that warrants closer coordination.

More generally, the limitations of existing support infrastructures and resources (see section 5.1) suggest a **research and action agenda**, including comparative mapping of national and institutional responses, integration of resilience- and solidarity-oriented interventions, work on how to handle criticism without either silencing publics or overburdening individual scientists, and more rigorous empirical investigations. Empirical research should use mixed-method designs combining interviews with affected scientists and other stakeholders, surveys, secondary analyses of administrative data, and experimental evaluation of specific interventions. Overall, a research and action agenda may want to address the following themes and questions:

- **Resilience.** What motivates scientists to continue engaging publicly in the face of backlash, and what individual, collegial, institutional, and contextual factors strengthen their resilience? Are these factors similar to or distinct from those identified for journalists and politicians? How can we leverage these factors to make less resilient scientists and science communicators more resilient?
- **Effectiveness measurement.** How can robust, comparable key performance indicators of countermeasure effectiveness be developed, so that university leaders can make objective, comparative assessments of the strengths and weaknesses of their institutional response systems?

- **Science communication professionals.** What role do communications officers, press officers, and dedicated science-communication staff at universities play in absorbing backlash, what support do they themselves need, and how can their work be strengthened, both in terms of informal acknowledgement and financial support?
- **Independent and non-affiliated researchers.** How can support reach researchers without an institutional employer, who are currently outside the WetenschapVeilig pathway and similar institutionally mediated mechanisms?
- **System-level measures.** Which structural measures, beyond contact points, are required, for example, dedicated legislation classifying attacks on scientists as an aggravated offence (as in several EU jurisdictions for politicians), platform-regulation provisions, or coordinated criminal-justice protocols similar to those of PersVeilig?
- **Coordination across levels.** How can individual-level (e.g., peer support), institution-level (e.g., university contact persons, communications officers, confidential advisors), and national-level (e.g., UNL/WetenschapVeilig) responses be coordinated to avoid both diffusion of responsibility and cannibalization, while preserving the flexibility needed for individual circumstances?
- **International role.** How can the Netherlands, with its comparatively developed infrastructure and role in UNESCO's Programme on the Freedom and Safety of Scientists, serve as a peer model for countries where backlash response is less developed?

Structural efforts would substantially advance answers to most of these questions and would also serve as a model that can be exported to other contexts via UNESCO, the Universities of the Netherlands, and European research-integrity networks.

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Appendix: Overview of Initiatives and Resources

Resources are sorted by type, in the following order: Support platforms and practice-oriented projects; international programs; practical guides, handbooks, toolkits; resource hubs; position papers/advocacy. Version: 30th May 2026.

Resource / Initiative	Parent Organization(s)	Year	Type	Geographic Scope	Description	Reference
WetenschapVeilig (SafeScience)	Universities of the Netherlands (UNL)	2022	Support platforms and practice-oriented projects	Netherlands	24/7 online and telephone hotline; routes reports to the affected scholar's employer; provides emergency line and tips for academics, staff, and employers.	WetenschapVeilig. (2022). <i>WetenschapVeilig: Meldpunt voor bedreigde, geïntimideerde of lastiggevallen wetenschappers</i> [SafeScience: Reporting point for threatened, intimidated, or harassed scientists]. Universities of the Netherlands, NWO, & KNAW. https://www.wetenschapveilig.nl/
Scicomm-Support	Bundesverband Hochschulkommunikation (BV_HKOM); German Research Foundation (DFG); German Rectors' Conference (HRK)	2023	Support platforms and practice-oriented projects	Germany, Austria, Switzerland	Helpline for scientists and science communicators; provides guidelines and legal advice; offers trainings, workshops, and consultation.	Scicomm-Support. (2023). <i>Scicomm-Support</i> . https://scicomm-support.de/en/
KAPAZ (Capacities and Competencies in Dealing with Hate Speech and Hostility towards Science)	Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society (HIIG)	2023	Support platforms and practice-oriented projects	Germany	Multi-partner project combining research and practice; representative survey of researchers; legal opinion on institutional duties; train-the-trainer programs; summer school.	HIIG. (2025). <i>KAPAZ: Capacities and competencies in dealing with hate speech and hostility towards science</i> . Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society. https://www.hiig.de/en/project/hostility-towards-science-capaz/
UNESCO Programme on the Freedom and Safety of Scientists	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO)	2024	International programs	Global	Launched in 2023–2024 with the Netherlands as a driver; flagship report sets out a typology of threats; Call to Action endorsed by 60+ Member States; offers an international exchange platform.	UNESCO. (2024). <i>The safety of scientific researchers: Data, trends and a typology of threats</i> . United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. https://doi.org/10.54678/BXCC9984
Inspireurope	Scholars at Risk Europe (funded under the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe programs)	2022	International programs	Europe	Coordinates support for researchers at risk; trains 300+ researchers; advises 400+ employers; informs EU and national policy.	SAR Europe. (2025). <i>Inspireurope – Support researchers at risk</i> . https://sareurope.eu/what-we-do/inspireurope-support-researchers-at-risk/

Resource / Initiative	Parent Organization(s)	Year	Type	Geographic Scope	Description	Reference
Freedom from Harassment for Scientists is Essential – Awareness Raising and Advice	PREPARED project (funded under the Horizon Europe program)	2025	Practical guides, handbooks, toolkits	Europe	Awareness-raising and questions-with-advice format covering online and in-person harassment; produced as part of the Horizon Europe PREPARED project.	Schroeder, D., Chatfield, K., Videnoja, K., Partington, H., Singh, M., Seedall, C., Marcou, A., Evans, N., Sairio, A., & Andanda, P. (2025). <i>Freedom from harassment for scientists is essential</i> (Report for PREPARED). https://prepared-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/Freedom-from-harassment-for-scientists-is-essential-final.pdf
Dutch Universities Guide for Protecting Scientists Against (Online) Threats and Intimidation	Universities of the Netherlands (then VSNU)	2021	Practical guides, handbooks, toolkits	Netherlands	Practical handbook accompanying WetenschapVeilig; sets out concrete actions for institutions, supervisors, communications offices, and individual scientists facing online or physical threats and intimidation; informed by PersVeilig.	UNL. (2021). <i>Dutch universities guide for protecting scientists against (online) threats and intimidation</i> . Universities of the Netherlands. https://www.wetenschapveilig.nl/documenten/vsnu_handreiking_aanpak_bedreiging_wetenschappers_eng.pdf
Umgang mit rechten Anfeindungen gegen die Wissenschaft [Dealing with right-wing hostility toward science.]	GERDEA-Forschungsverbund; Bundesverband Mobile Beratung e.V.	2025	Practical guides, handbooks, toolkits	Germany	Practical handbook addressing right-wing hostility; combines a democratic-theory framing with consulting practice from the Mobile Beratung network and ten recommendations for individuals and institutions; includes a directory of support resources.	GERDEA-Forschungsverbund und Bundesverband Mobile Beratung e.V. (2025). <i>Umgang mit rechten Anfeindungen gegen die Wissenschaft</i> [Dealing with right-wing hostility against science]. https://www.projekt-gerdea.de/publikationen/umgang-mit-rechten-anfeindungen-gegen-die-wissenschaft
Researcher Support Consortium Toolkit for Institutions	Researcher Support Consortium (PEN America, FFR, Knight Institute, IFEX, and academic partners)	2024	Practical guides, handbooks, toolkits	US / International	Step-by-step institutional guide including policy templates, support team composition, communication strategy, incident response, FOIA management, and reporting form.	Researcher Support Consortium. (2024). <i>RSC toolkit for institutions (V2)</i> . https://researchersupport.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/RSC_Toolkit_V2.pdf
AoIR Risky Research Guide	Association of Internet Researchers (AoIR)	2025	Practical guides, handbooks, toolkits	International	Risk-assessment frameworks; mitigation strategies; recommendations for departments and supervisors; tailored to scholars working on disinformation, extremism, LGBTQ+ rights, climate, and platform governance.	AoIR. (2025). <i>Risky research: An AoIR guide to researcher protection and safety 2025</i> . Association of Internet Researchers. https://aoir.org/riskyresearchguide/

Resource / Initiative	Parent Organization(s)	Year	Type	Geographic Scope	Description	Reference
Society for Neuroscience. Best Practices for Protecting Researchers and Research	Society for Neuroscience (SfN)	2024	Practical guides, handbooks, toolkits	US / International	Sectoral best-practice document with practical advice for researchers using animal models facing organized backlash.	SfN. (2024). <i>Best practices for protecting researchers and research</i> . Society for Neuroscience. https://www.sfn.org/-/media/SfN/Documents/NEW-SfN/Initiatives/Animals-in-Research/Best-Practices-for-Protecting-Researchers-and-Research.pdf
Recommendations: When Your Research Is Attacked	Civic Laboratory for Environmental Action Research (CLEAR)	2025	Practical guides, handbooks, toolkits	International	Researcher-led public guide synthesizing institutional, peer, and self-protection strategies, with attention to environmental and decolonial research.	CLEAR. (2025, January 3). <i>When your research is attacked</i> . Civic Laboratory for Environmental Action Research. https://civiclaboratory.nl/2025/01/03/when-your-research-is-attacked/
Advice for Researchers Experiencing Harassment	Science Media Centre UK	2019	Practical guides, handbooks, toolkits	UK / International	Practical guide on engaging the media constructively when targeted; supports researchers facing harassment in controversial fields (climate, animal research, gender).	Science Media Centre UK. (2019). <i>Advice for researchers experiencing harassment</i> . https://www.sciencemediacentre.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Advice-for-Researchers-Experiencing-Harrasment-2019.pdf
Handling Online Harassment Online Toolkit	Australian Science Media Centre (AusSMC)	2024	Practical guides, handbooks, toolkits	Australia and New Zealand	Modular online resource accessible via the Science Media SAVVY platform; helps researchers prepare for and respond to trolling and online harassment, with login by university email.	Australian Science Media Centre. (2024). <i>Handling online harassment</i> [Online toolkit]. Science Media SAVVY. https://sciencemediasavvy.org/handling-online-harassment
PEN America Online Harassment Field Manual	PEN America	2018	Practical guides, handbooks, toolkits	International	Comprehensive guide on digital hygiene, doxxing prevention, social-media safety, legal options, and supporting targets.	PEN America. (2024). <i>Online harassment field manual</i> . https://onlineharassmentfieldmanual.pen.org/
Don't Feed the Trolls: How to Deal with Hate on Social Media	Center for Countering Digital Hate (CCDH)	2019	Practical guides, handbooks, toolkits	International	Practitioner-oriented handbook; sets out a harm-minimization framework for those targeted by coordinated online trolling; explains why engagement may amplify hate and offers concrete counterstrategies.	Center for Countering Digital Hate. (2019). <i>Don't feed the trolls: How to deal with hate on social media</i> . https://counterhate.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/Dont-Feed-the-Trolls.pdf

Resource / Initiative	Parent Organization(s)	Year	Type	Geographic Scope	Description	Reference
Online harassment: A toolkit for protecting yourself from abuse	Nature	2022	Practical guides, handbooks, toolkits	International	Career feature serving as a toolkit; practical advice for scientists on preventing and responding to online abuse; covers digital hygiene, response strategies, and institutional engagement.	Nogrady, B. (2022). Online harassment: A toolkit for protecting yourself from abuse. <i>Nature</i> , 609(7926), 205–207. https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-02766-w
Online Harassment Guide for Researchers	Taylor & Francis Group	2024	Practical guides, handbooks, toolkits	International	Publisher-led practical guide providing advice to authors and researchers facing online harassment.	Taylor & Francis Group. (2024, October 3). <i>New guide offers support and advice to researchers experiencing online harassment</i> . https://newsroom.taylorandfrancisgroup.com/new-guide-offers-support-and-advice-to-researchers-experiencing-online-harassment/
Misogyny and Extremism: Mitigation Efforts for Researchers	ASIS International	2026	Practical guides, handbooks, toolkits	International	Practitioner article discussing physical and digital security strategies for researchers facing misogyny-driven extremism.	ASIS International. (2026, March). Misogyny and extremism: Mitigation efforts for researchers. <i>Security Management</i> . https://www.asisonline.org/security-management-magazine/articles/2026/03/misogyny-and-extremism/mitigation-efforts-for-researchers/
Resources for Researchers and Scholars Under Threat	National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (NASEM)	2025	Resource hubs	US / International	Aggregates legal, communications, security, and mental-health resources for affected scholars.	NASEM. (2025). <i>Resources for researchers and scholars under threat in the United States</i> . National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. https://www.nationalacademies.org/resources-for-researchers-and-scholars-under-threat-in-the-united-states
UCS vs. Anti-Science Actions tracker	Union of Concerned Scientists (UCS)	2026	Resource hubs	US	Litigation tracker and advocacy resource; tracks legal challenges to government actions perceived as suppressing or politicizing science; relevant for monitoring systemic political pressure.	Union of Concerned Scientists. (2026, March 19). <i>UCS vs. anti-science actions: Lawsuits and legal action to defend science</i> . https://www.ucs.org/resources/ucs-vs-anti-science-actions
Academic freedom in the Netherlands: A response to current threats	Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW)	2025	Position papers / Advocacy	Netherlands	Report on academic freedom and intimidation (2025), preceded by reports on social safety in Dutch science (2022), and knowledge security (2023).	KNAW. (2025). <i>Academische vrijheid in Nederland: Reactie op actuele bedreigingen</i> [Academic freedom in the Netherlands: A response to current threats]. Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences. https://www.knaw.nl/themas/academische-vrijheid

Resource / Initiative	Parent Organization(s)	Year	Type	Geographic Scope	Description	Reference
CSDI Policy Brief: How Universities Can Better Address Online Harassment	Centre for the Study of Democratic Institutions, University of British Columbia	2025	Position papers / Advocacy	Canada / International	Proposes an institutional support framework spanning physical safety, cybersecurity, mental health, communications, legal, equity, and HR.	Mathews, N., Tenove, C., Tworek, H., Guyn, C., & Hodson, J. (2025). <i>How universities can better address online harassment</i> [Policy brief]. Centre for the Study of Democratic Institutions, University of British Columbia. https://democracy.ubc.ca/wp-content/uploads/sites/65/2025/11/CSDI-Policy-Brief-Online-Abuse.pdf
Protecting Expert Advice for the Public: Promoting Safety and Improved Communications	Royal Society of Canada	2022	Position papers / Advocacy	Canada	Seven recommendations addressing federal funding agencies, the federal government, and the postsecondary sector; calls for a more nuanced approach to knowledge-mobilization requirements that takes researcher safety into account.	Wright, J. M., Chun, W. H. K., Clarke, A., Herder, M., & Ramos, H. (2022). Protecting expert advice for the public: Promoting safety and improved communications. <i>FACETS</i> , 7, 482–508. https://doi.org/10.1139/facets-2021-0181